

Clinical Audit on Medial Meniscal Posterior Root Tear Repair in a Tertiary Care HospitalY G Raghava Naidu¹, Saya Venkateswara Prasad², Battu Maheswara Reddy³, Nagesh Muddamsetti⁴¹Assistant Professor of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh²Associate Professor of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh³Assistant Professor of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh⁴Assistant Professor of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Meniscal root tears lead to significant functional impairment and increase the risk of osteoarthritis. Repairing the root aims to restore knee anatomy and biomechanics, thus reducing osteo-arthritic progression. While several techniques for root repair exist, challenges remain with bed preparation and instrumentation.**Aim of the study:** Present study evaluated the early clinical results of root re-insertion using an accessory supra-meniscal portal, which aided in preparation and instrumentation of the bed.**Materials:** From February 2022 to January 2024 22 patients aged between 18 to 77 years with medial meniscus root tears underwent arthroscopic root repair using heavy braided sutures passed through a tibial tunnel and tied over a bone button. An accessory supra-meniscal portal was utilized for improved visualization and suture management. Patients were followed for 24 months, and functional outcomes were assessed using the Lysholm Knee Score.**Results:** After 24-month follow-up, the mean Lysholm score improved significantly from 81.5 ± 08.61 preoperatively to 90.25 ± 5.60 postoperatively ($p = 0.001$). Traumatic tears had higher preoperative and postoperative Lysholm scores compared to degenerative tears. Aged patients showed poorer functional outcomes.**Conclusion:** Medial meniscal root re-insertion restores knee function and helps prevent arthritis progression. Traumatic tears, especially in younger patients, show more significant improvements compared to degenerative tears.**Keywords:** Medial Meniscus, meniscus root, osteoarthritis, knee arthroscopy, Tears of menisci, Lyshom score and tibial tunnel.

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Introduction

Meniscal root tears significantly disrupt knee biomechanics, leading to increased tibio-femoral contact and stress, which accelerates osteoarthritis. [1] While partial Meniscectomy may alleviate symptoms in the short term, but often leads to progressive arthritis. [2] Root repair, in contrast, offers long-term benefits by restoring the meniscus' function. [3]

Several surgical techniques have been described and used for root repair, each with its strengths and limitations. [4] Among these, anterior portal techniques are challenging due to potential

cartilage injury [5], while posterior portal techniques provide better visualization and alignment but can be technically demanding. [6] Meniscus root tears are significant in the context of all meniscal injuries for two main reasons: they account for an estimated 10% to 21% of all meniscal tears. [7] From a biomechanical perspective, the meniscus roots play a critical role in converting and distributing axial tibio-femoral loads as hoop stresses. [8]

These structures are essential for the proper function of the menisci and, consequently, for knee

biomechanics, as the menisci absorb 50% to 70% of the loads experienced by the medial and lateral compartments. [9] When the meniscus root is torn, it leads to extrusion of the meniscus, disrupting the force distribution across the tibial plateau due to the loss of hoop stress. [10] This disruption results in abnormal, high-peak tibio-femoral contact pressures and decreased contact areas, which can contribute to degenerative cartilage damage. [11] The loss of the meniscus root attachment and its associated function creates a biomechanical condition similar to that of a total Meniscectomy. [12]

Materials: Between February 2022 and January 2024 22 patients with medial meniscus root tears were included in the study. An ethics committee approval was obtained before commencing the study. An ethics committee approved proforma was used for the study.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients of all age groups above 18 years were included. Patients with Traumatic or symptomatic degenerative tears with signs of medial compartment overload (e.g., subchondral marrow edema on MRI) were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below the age of 77 were excluded. Patients with Chondral degeneration (grade 3 or higher), osteoarthritis, obesity, or varus mal-alignment were excluded. All patients underwent preoperative evaluation with clinical assessment (Lysholm score) and MRI to confirm the diagnosis. Intra-operative arthroscopy was performed via standard anterolateral and anteromedial portals, and an accessory supra-meniscal portal was established to facilitate root tear repair. The meniscal root bed was prepared, and sutures were passed using a suture passer through a tibial tunnel and tied over a bone button.

Surgical Technique: Following informed consent, surgery was performed under general or spinal anesthesia in the supine position. The diagnostic arthroscopy confirmed the root tear and assessed the meniscal and chondral status. A combination of shaver and curette was used to prepare the root bed. The supra-meniscal portal, as described by Seifeldin and Khedr, provided a clear trajectory for suture management and minimized the risk of chondral damage. A suture passer was introduced through the supra-meniscal portal to capture the meniscal root, and sutures were passed using either a double cinch or horizontal mattress technique. The tibial tunnel was created using a beath pin and an ACL guide, and the sutures were shuttled through the tunnel and tied over a bone button for secure fixation.

Postoperative care: An extension brace is applied for 4 weeks. Early isometric quadriceps exercise and achieving full knee extension are strongly

encouraged. Patients are not allowed to bear weight for 6 weeks. Flexion range is permitted to 70° for the first 6 weeks and gradually increased to 120 thereafter. This is followed by a gradual muscle strengthening and balancing program. Deep squats are not allowed before 3–4 months. Routine anticoagulation was prescribed for at least 3 weeks and up to 6 weeks guided by the patients' status and co morbidities. Cryotherapy was highly advised to reduce swelling and pain in the first 1–2 weeks after arthroscopy. Tegner Lysholm's score was evaluated at the final follow-up at 24 months.

Statistical methods: The data were analyzed using the statistical package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26 (IBM Corp. Standard statistical methods and units were used such as mean, SD, median, minimum, and maximum in quantitative data. Comparisons between quantitative variables were done using the nonparametric Mann–Whitney test. Correlations between quantitative variables were done using the Spearman correlation coefficient. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results:

Among the 22 patients selected for the study 12 (54.54%) were males and 09 (40.90%) were females. The mean age was 44.7± 2.35 years among the males and 46.85±4.20 in the females. 16 (72.72%) patients had traumatic root tears; while 06 (27.27%) had degenerative tears. 18/22 (81.81%) patients had no significant medial compartment osteoarthritic changes, although 04 (18.18%) patients exhibited mild to moderate degenerative changes (Outer bridge grade 1 or 2). All the patients were followed up for a period of 24 months. Preoperatively, the mean Lysholm score was 81.5 ± 08.61 preoperatively to 90.25 ± 5.60 postoperatively (p = 0.001). Of the patients, 19 (86.36%) had excellent outcomes, 02 (09.09%) had a good outcome, and 01 (04.5%) had a fair outcome. Among the 22 patients no patient showed signs of Mc-Murrays test positive or had any effusion or catching/locking at the final follow-up. 03 (13.63%) patients experienced mild pain on the medial aspect of the joint line and pain on climbing stairs, squatting, and walking long distances. These were the patients who showed lower Lysholm scores. These three patients were among those who had degenerative tears with grade 2 medial compartment changes at the time of the index procedure. The mean± SD postoperative Lysholm score at the final follow-up was 91.55±3.90. A total of 19 (86.36%) patients were excellent on the Lysholm score, 01 (04.5%) was good, and 01 (04.5%) had fair results. This shows a statistically significant improvement as compared with the preoperative Lysholm score after root repair, with a P value of less than 0.001 (Table 1).

Table 1: Showing the demographic data and Lysholm scores in the patients (n-22)

Observation	Number	Percentage	P value
Age			0.124
18 to 37 Yrs	05		
38 to 57 Yrs	13		
58 to 77 Yrs	04		
Gender			0.215
Male	12		
Female	08		
Traumatic Meniscal tear	16		0.001
Degenerative Meniscal tear	06		0.001
Pre-operative Lysholm score	81.5 ± 08.61		0.001
Post-operative Lysholm score	90.25 ± 5.60		0.001

When the patients of traumatic Meniscus tears and degenerative meniscus tears are treated as two different groups, it was observed that the traumatic degenerative patients had the mean preoperative and postoperative Lysholm scores at a higher score. Similarly the amount of improvement was marginally higher for the traumatic patients as

compared with those with degenerative tears; this was not statistically significant, with a P value of 0.758 preoperatively and 0.299 postoperatively in the study. It was also found that the mean age for traumatic patients was statistically lower, with P value of 0.002, as compared with the degenerative group, which showed a higher mean age (Table 2).

Table 2: Showing the comparison between traumatic and degenerative groups treated for Meniscal injuries (n-22).

Observation	Traumatic Meniscal injury	Degenerative meniscal injury
Pre-operative Lysholm score	82.5 ± 06.41	83.5 ± 05.30
Post-operative Lysholm score	92.25 ± 4.20	91.25 ± 3.10
P value	0.758	0.299
Mean Age	53.64±5.50	51.23±3.38
P value	0.002	0.002

The traumatic root tears in the study showed greater improvement in functional scores compared to degenerative tears, though the difference was not statistically significant. (p value more than 0.05) A significant correlation was found between age and postoperative outcomes, with older patients showing poorer functional results. There was no significant difference between male and female patients regarding functional outcomes.

Discussion

In this study 22 patients with root tears, we observed a statistically significant improvement in the postoperative Lysholm score compared to preoperative values. These finding aligned with studies by Kim et al., Moon et al., and Seo et al. [13, 14 and 15] The study showed that the mean preoperative Lysholm score was lower in traumatic cases compared to degenerative cases, although the difference was not statistically significant. Interestingly, the mean postoperative Lysholm score was higher in traumatic cases, showing greater improvement, though this difference was also not statistically significant.

To our knowledge, our study is the first to stratify functional outcomes based on the type of tear—traumatic versus degenerative—demonstrating greater improvement in the traumatic group.

Additionally, it was observed that a significant correlation was present between medial compartment osteoarthritis and degenerative tears. Seo et al.'s [14] study used second-look arthroscopy to objectively report healing rates following root repair, which is considered strength of their study. However, it could be that, the technique they used may account for their relatively low healing rates and some doubts regarding the value of root repair. Jung et al. [16] reported on 13 patients who underwent root repair using suture anchors, with a slightly longer follow-up (average 30.8 months).

They used a high postero-medial portal for anchor placement, a technique we consider time-consuming, technically demanding, and potentially risky to neurovascular structures. However the technique used in this study was safer, quicker, and less technically complex. Jung et al. suggested that avoiding tibial tunnels helps prevent failure or lax healing due to the wind-shield effect on the suspension suture. [16] Jung et al.'s [16] technique left knots tied intra-articularly, which we believe could lead to complications like knee pain, catching, or squeaking, contributing to patient dissatisfaction. They used fiber-wire, which is strong and comparable to the suture material used in our series. We agree that fiber-wire is superior to

PDS, which is used in other studies and produces better outcomes. Moon et al. [16] performed root repair on 77 patients using the pull-out suture technique with PDS no. 2 sutures. Their sample size was much larger than ours, and they also performed routine medial release to avoid chondral injury. They used a single suture pass through the meniscus, drilling two tunnels. Our final mean Lysholm score (91.55 ± 3.90) is higher than Moon et al.'s [14] mean score of 83.2 ± 16.1 . This difference may be due to our use of heavy braided suture material, which is stronger than PDS, which loses 40% of its tensile strength over time. Kim et al. [12] demonstrated a reduction in meniscal extrusion after root repair, which they attributed to a high healing rate (17 out of 30) on MRI and good-quality healing observed on second-look arthroscopy (9 out of 14). While many techniques are available for root repair, it was advocated in this study to use the accessory supra-meniscal portal.

This method provides superior access to the root tear, reduces the risk of chondral injury, and avoids the complexities of posterior portals. In addition, the use of heavy braided sutures for fixation offers better stability than other suture materials, such as PDS, which lose tensile strength over time.

Limitations of the study:

The lack of MRI or second-look arthroscopy to assess meniscal healing was the main limitation of this study. However, clinical outcomes and functional scores showed clear improvement, suggesting successful healing and biomechanical restoration.

Conclusion

Medial meniscal root repair significantly improves knee function and may help prevent osteoarthritis progression. Younger patients and those with traumatic tears tend to have better outcomes. Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-ups are needed to confirm the long-term efficacy of root repair, and the role of adjunct procedures such as high tibial osteotomy should be explored.

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